

Resilience effects on the self-development of adolescents in secondary schools in Kumba, Cameroon

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated into resilience effects on the self-development of adolescents in secondary schools in Kumba II Sub Division of South West, Cameroon. Focus was on adaptation, locus of control, self-efficacy and persistence and their relationship with self-development. The descriptive survey design was used with a sample of 303 adolescent students. The instrument used for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire with a reliability of 0.712. Data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages and Spearman rho test to establish relationships between resilience and self-development. The findings showed a significant and positive relationship between adaptation and self-development ($P\text{-value}=0.048<0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R=0.211$) implied that self-development was more likely when adolescents were well adapted in their environment. Findings equally affirmed that there was a significant and positive relationship between locus of control and self-development ($P\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R=0.235$) implied that self-development was more likely when they adequately control their behavior in their environment. Similarly, the findings equally revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between self-efficacy and self-development ($P\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R=0.311$) implied that self-development was more likely when they portray high self-efficacy about their own self. Finally, the findings on persistence revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between persistence and self-development ($P\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R=0.244$) implied that self-development was more likely when they portray high level of persistence in their environment. The findings indicated that resilience therefore has an effect on the self-development of adolescents in secondary schools in Kumba. Based on the findings, some recommendations were made that the government should sensitize adolescents on forums to be resilient because the findings of this study have showed that adolescents are endowed with resilient potentials. Adolescents should be seen as contributors to the welfare of society not passive agents. Seminars, workshops, refresher courses could be organized to educate adolescents on issues that will help deviate their minds from deviant behaviours and juvenile delinquency and to be more engage in activities that can add values in their lives and improve on their self-development.

Keywords: *Resilience, self-development, adolescents, adaptation, locus of control, persistence and self-efficacy.*

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INTRODUCTION

Resilience research has evolved as a major theme in developmental psychology in general and positive development research in particular. Its focus is on why some children and adolescents adapt positively despite their experience of distressing and demanding life conditions and risks such as violence, poverty, stress, trauma, deprivation, and oppression [1]. Such research see resilience as a key variable in predicting positive outcomes in the face of adversity [2]. In resilience research, three waves of research have been identified including exposure to threatening or risk factors; protective factors that help ameliorate the impact of risk factors; and the achievement of positive adaptation through competence building in various domains [3]. These waves of research have contributed significantly in terms of concepts, methods, findings, issues, controversies, and clues that are useful in promoting the fourth wave which focuses on multiple analyses and the dynamics of adaptation and change [4, 2].

Resilience is a dynamic set of skills utilized when facing a difficult situation, encompassing a range of thoughts (positive outlook), feelings and behaviours [5]. It can still be a process consisting of positive adaptation when faced with significant hardship, or adversity. It is the process of overcoming the negative effects of risk exposure, coping successfully with traumatic experiences, and avoiding the negative trajectories associated with risks [6]. A key requirement of resilience is the presence of both risks and promotive factors that either help bring about a positive outcome or reduce or avoid a negative outcome [7]. Resilience though concerned with risk exposure among adolescents, is focused on strengths rather than deficits. It focuses on understanding healthy development in spite of exposure to risk [7].

Masten, Best, and Garmezy [8] viewed resilience as the process of, capacity for, or outcome of successful adaptation despite challenging or threatening circumstances. Since then, difficulties in defining resilience have become more widely recognized due to differences in environments and differences in individuals' personal traits [9, 2]. In explaining why some children and adolescents maintain positive adaptation even though they grow up in deprived, troubled, and threatening environments, differences in measuring the significance, quality, and quantity of adversities as well as positive adjustment are commonly found. The American Psychological Association [10] also uses a broad definition: the process of adapting well in the face of adversity, trauma, tragedy, threats, or even significant sources of stress—such as family and relationship problems, serious health problems, or workplace and financial stressors. It means “bouncing back” from difficult experiences [10].

Resilience occurs when environmental, social, and individual factors interrupt the trajectory from risk to pathology. Such variables have been called promotive factors because they are associated with positive development and help adolescents overcome adversity [11]. Resilience theory also emphasizes a strengths-based approach to developing preventive interventions because it concentrates on enhancing promotive factors instead of reducing exposure to risk or ameliorating deficits in adolescents [12]. The promotive factors that can help youth and adolescents avoid the negative effects of risks may be either assets or resources. Assets include the individual's psychological capital or the positive factors that reside within the adolescent, such as competence, coping skills, and self-efficacy [13]. Meanwhile, resources are also positive factors that help individuals overcome risk, but they are external to the individual. Resources include parental support, adult mentoring, or community organizations that promote the positive development children and youth as well as the adult and ageing populations.

Elliot and Gramling [14] found that resilience helps adolescent students to lessen depression, anxiety, stress and psychological problems which have a significant impact on their self-development and achievement. According to them, individuals who adapt very well despite facing risks and those with maladaptation benefit from protective factors. Thus, enhancing both internal and external protective factors of adolescents may help them adapt to stressful and risky life situations. For internal protective factors, research findings show that optimism, perceptions of control, self-efficacy, and active coping are associated with better health [15].

Grotberg [16] cited longitudinal studies to show that about half to two-thirds of adolescents with resilience could overcome their initial traumatic life experiences, such as growing up in families with a mentally ill member, being abused, or having criminally involved parents. Thus, cultivating resilience is an important way to promote the psychological and social development of adolescents. For external protective factors, theorists have suggested that people who do not have a functional social support system are more vulnerable to external stressors [17]. Therefore, it is important to strengthen an individual's ability to recognize and utilize social support systems in his or her surroundings. Meanwhile self-development involves encouraging each individual to become personally, emotionally, socially and physically effective to live healthy, safe and fulfilled lives and to become confident, independent and responsible citizens, making informed and responsible choices and decisions throughout their lives [18]. According to Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi [19], self-development is taking steps to better yourself, such as learning new skills or overcoming bad habits. It is a process of improving or developing one's self including activities that create awareness and identity, talents and potentials, building human capital and facilitating employability, enhancing quality of life and contributing to the realization of dreams and aspirations [18]. It is therefore important for adolescents to find things in life that excite and motivate them and that can move them quickly into success and happiness. Hawkins [20] views self-development as encouraging each individual to become personally, emotionally, socially and physically effective, to live healthy, safe and fulfilled lives; and to become confident, independent and responsible citizens, making informed and responsible choices and decisions throughout their lives. The concept involves formal and informal activities for developing others in roles such as teacher, guide, counselor, manager, life coach or mentor. When personal development takes place in the context of institutions, it refers to the methods, programs, tools, techniques, and assessment systems that support human development at the individual level in organizations [21].

In studying resilience, there are three critical conditions: growing up in distressing life conditions, the availability of protective factors, including internal assets and external resources that may be associated with counteracting the effects of risk factors, and the achievement of positive adaptation despite experiences of significant adversity [2]. Richardson [22] contends that resilience is the process of coping with disruptive, stressful, or challenging life events in a way that provides the individual with additional protective and coping skills than prior to the disruption that results from the event. Similarly, Higgins [23] describes resilience as the process of self-righting or growth, while Wolins [24] defines it as the capacity to bounce back, to withstand hardship, and to repair yourself.

According to Messler & Capobianco [25], the ability to adapt effectively with anxiety and stress is another skill which differentiates low-risk from high-risk young people. Effective adaptability skills influence the individual's response to stress, which in turn affects the way that individual deals with conflict with others. Depending on the young

person's adaptability and problem-solving skills, adolescents could either adapt with humour, altruism or by focusing their attention elsewhere, or they could withdraw or simply act out [25]. This view is reinforced by Masten, Best and Garmezy [8] and Lewis [26] who suggested that adolescents who display resilience demonstrate the capacity of adapting in all problems. Catalano, Berglund, Ryan, Lonczak, and Hawkins [27] argued that adolescents who adapt well are always less stressful thereby given them healthy development. Resilience factors that were considered in the present study included self-efficacy, persistence, locus of control and adaptation.

According to Bandura [28] self-efficacy is the belief in one's own ability to successfully accomplish something. Self-efficacy tells us that people generally will only attempt things they believe they can accomplish and will not attempt things they believe they will fail. According to Bandura [29] self-efficacy involves individuals' beliefs about their ability to successfully engage in a task in order to obtain a desired outcome. He asserted that self-efficacy is important because individuals' with high self-efficacy for a task tend to try harder at the task and experience more positive emotions relating to the task. According to Bandura [30], self-efficacy is a personal judgment of how well one can execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situations. Expectations of self-efficacy determine whether an individual will be able to exhibit coping behaviour and how long effort will be sustained in the face of obstacles. Individuals who have high self-efficacy will exert sufficient effort that, if well executed, leads to successful outcomes, whereas those with low self-efficacy are likely to cease effort early and fail. Psychologists have studied self-efficacy from several perspectives, noting various paths in the development of self-efficacy; the dynamics of self-efficacy; interactions between self-efficacy and self-concept; and habits of attribution that contribute to or detract from self-efficacy.

Some of such studies have found purported links between self-efficacy and self-development indicators. For instance, in their study of agency and self-development, Lo-oh & Busi [31] found enough statistical evidence between self-efficacy and self-development potentials of university students. Masten & Obradovic [32] also found links between self-efficacy and adaptation at school, and Pajeres & Schunk [33] found that self-efficacy bears a positive relation to individual educational and learning outcomes. And in this connection, Papinczak et al. [34] found links between high self-efficacy and deep learning approaches while students with low self-efficacy were more inclined to surface level learning approaches. That is why Caprara, Fida, Vecchione, Bove, Vecchio, Barbaranelli & Bandura [35] found relationships between perceived self-efficacy and self-regulatory learning as well as academic achievement. Chen [36] found links between self-efficacy, motivation and personal agency arguing that they become key empowerment drivers and agents of self-development. Meanwhile Vries [37] maintained that low self-efficacy predicted higher levels of depression, Bandura [38] argued that persons with high self-efficacy abilities set challenging goals and stay committed even in the face of adversities with sustained efforts towards success. And Yelsma & Yelsma [39] added that adolescents with high self-efficacy beliefs prefer difficult circumstances, appear to be quite sure of their personal efforts leading to success, and are less sensitive to emotional turbulence or affected by depression.

Persistence on the other hand is a personality trait that causes a person to persevere in a task despite obstacles or frustrations rather than simply giving up [40]. Persistence is a voluntary continuation of a goal-directed action in spite of obstacles, difficulties, or discouragement [41]. Just as fear is a prerequisite for courage, challenge is a prerequisite for perseverance. According to Wong [42], adolescents are more likely to persist in their goal pursuit, when many response options are available; they persist as long as they are free to explore alternative pathways to success. However, they are less likely to persist, when there are more competing goals to distract them. Hoppe [43] represents persistence as a person's expectations, goals, claims or his future achievement in a given task. He further stresses that the "experiences of performance" as a success of failure does not depend upon its objective goodness alone but also on the persistence reached. Furthermore, Morrow & Ackermann [44] argued that social environment is a predictor of adolescent persistence. As sense of community, developed through positive interactions with other members of the adolescent or college community, promotes adjustment to the demands of college. Tinto [45] highlighted the utility of college or adolescent subcultures and student-teachers interaction in reducing student departure from college. It has been noted that greater integration with the school community is essential to academic success. In fact, living on campus dramatically increases the odds of a student persisting to continue and aspiring to succeed.

When checked against each other, persistence has been shown to influence self-development indicators in various ways. For instance, Altman [46] found links between persistent behaviour and the academic achievement of university students, and concluded like many other studies that persistence is a primary measure of success at school especially for students studying in difficult circumstances. Edwards & Beattie [47] also found relationships between persistence and student success in developmental mathematics pathways, and productivity persistence promote student social mindsets, and effective learning strategies. Finally, and in this direction, Kay, Nathan & Courtney [48] also found that students who engaged by persistence learned at higher levels and set and attained higher academic goals. They further related persistence to personal involvement, integration, quality of effort, effective learning and academic attainment, all measures of self-development.

Locus of control refers to people's premise on controlling their lives. According to Rotter [49], locus of control is the belief regarding whether internal or outside forces have control over their success or failure. If people hold themselves responsible for what they live, their locus of control is internal. If they hold outside events responsible for what they live, it is external [50]. People who have external locus of control determine their behaviour according to other people's wills, needs, perception and interpretations rather than their own. On the other hand, people who have internal locus of control determine their behaviour as to their own wills, needs, perception and interpretations. Research has shown that locus of control has an important role on adolescents self-development since it affects both psychological health and personality [51]. Adolescents with an internal locus of control hold internal factors responsible for their success or failure and as a result, they become more self-reliant in achieving their goals [52]. In addition, they are better at problem solving due to their believing in themselves. Conversely, individuals with an external locus of control believe their behaviour is the result of external factors like luck, fate, chance, and the people around them. Students with an external locus of control limit further improvement of their own skills, abilities, strengths, and weaknesses by relying on external factors. Similarly, those with external locus of control often view life as uncontrollable and difficult to cope with and often hold superstitious beliefs [52].

The relationship between locus of control and self-development is complex. Logically, adolescents who attribute success to internal factors are likely to expect future successes, while others who attribute failure to internal factors may expect future failure unless they consider themselves capable of actively address those factors [53]. Conversely, attributing success to external factors would make future successes unpredictable and deem the adolescent powerless to address what they perceive to be uncontrollable factors [53]. When Kutanis, Mesci & Ovdur [54] investigated links between locus of control and the self-development of learning outcomes, they found that internal locus of control yielded high learning outcomes and students with it were more protective and effective during teaching-learning processes. The reverse of external locus of control showed students who were more passive and reactive in the learning process. In line with this, Shepherd, Owen, Fitch, & Marshall [55] also found links between locus of control scores and academic achievement. Finally, in a study of locus of control, test anxiety, academic procrastination and achievement, Carden [56] found with the internal-external locus of control scale that students with internal locus of control showed lower academic procrastination, debilitating test anxiety and reported higher academic achievement than those with external locus of control.

Adaptation is conceived as an individual's ability to adjust and adapt to new experiences, especially with anxiety and stress [57]. Smit and Wandel [58] viewed adaptation as the development of genetic or behavioural characteristics, which enable an individual to cope with environmental changes and threats in order to survive. Effective adaptability skills influence the individual's response to stress which in turn affects the way the individual deals with conflicts with others [25]. Depending on the adaptability skill, the individual may either adapt with humour, altruistic behaviour or by focusing attention elsewhere, or simply withdraw or act out. Resilience findings show that adolescents who display resilience demonstrate the capacity to adapt to all problems they face [8]. And Catalano, Berglund, Ryan, Lonczak & Hawkins [27] felt that adolescents who adapt well are often less stressed up and score high on healthy development indices. Such individuals have a stronger internal locus of control, more confidence in their decision making ability and are less likely to be impulsive, ineffective and low-efficacy problem solvers.

The literature is clear that there are significant links between adaptive ability and engagement in risk-taking behaviours [59]. Meanwhile substantial research has demonstrated associations between peer pressure and sexual activity, smoking, substance use and abuse, gang involvement, delinquent behaviour and violence, significant research has also shown that young people with well developed adaptive skills score high in managing peer pressure with respect to all these anti-social behaviours [60,61]. Again, Seery [62] found close relationships between adaptation and adolescent student wellbeing, meaning that self-development could well be a product of adaptation. While protective factors were also found to influence adaptation, psychological wellbeing was significantly influenced by adaptation [33].

METHODS

The study was a descriptive survey and made use of a sample of 303 secondary schools students who were purposively and randomly selected. With purposive sampling we included participants who demonstrated a range of characteristics of adolescents including experience of adversity and some degree of resilience behaviour. Meanwhile random sampling was further used to select a number that was demographically representative and also sizable enough for the study.

The instrument used was a self-constructed questionnaire which was designed to collect data on resilience and the self-development of adolescents. Measures of resilience considered were adaptation, locus of control, self-efficacy and persistence.

Table 1: Reliability analysis

Conceptual	Cronbach's Alpha	Variance	Number of	Number of
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Components/variables	Coefficient		valid cases	valid items
Adaptation	0.612	0.049	15	10
Locus of control	0.568	0.062	15	10
Self-efficacy	0.517	0.040	14	10
Persistence	0.215	0.125	15	10
Self-development	0.492	0.057	15	10
Integrated value mapping	0.723	0.066	15	50

The reliability analysis report for the instrument was not violated for any of the conceptual components/variables with Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient values ranging from 0.642 to 0.781 with an integrated value mapping of 0.712.

Data were entered into a pre-designed Epi Data Version 3.1 [64] database which had an in-built consistency and validation checks were used to enter the data which was coded using serial numbers. For further consistency, data range and validation checks were performed in SPSS version 21.0 [65] to identify invalid codes (data cleaning). Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to present and analyse data. The Chi-square test was used to compare student's perceptions of conceptual components against demographic characteristics in order to appraise for significant differences. Hypotheses were verified using the Spearman Rho correlation. The Spearman rho correlation test was used to compare proportions in order to establish the predictive power of resilience over the self-development of adolescents in secondary schools in Kumba II subdivision of the South West Region of Cameroon.

FINDINGS

Findings showed that adaptation ($r=0.211$; $P=0.000$), locus of control ($r=0.235$; $P=0.000$), self-efficacy ($r=0.311$; $P=0.000$), and persistence ($r=0.244$; $P=0.000$) affected the self-development of adolescents in secondary schools in Kumba II Sub Division. The explanatory power of resilience indicators showed that self-efficacy was the highest predictor of self-development ($r=0.311$; $P=0.000$) whereas adaptation ($r=0.211$; $P=0.000$) had the lowest effect.

Fig.1. Comparing the effect of resilience indicators on self-development

Table 2: Summary of findings

Hypotheses	Statistical test	Comments
Hypothesis one (Ho1): There is no significant relationship between adaptation and the self-development of adolescents.	Spearman's rho test	Statistically, there was a significant and positive relationship between adaptation and self-development ($P\text{-value}=0.048<0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R=0.211^*$) implied self-development was more likely when they adapted better in their environment. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between adaptation and the self-development of adolescents was rejected and the alternative that there is a significant relationship between adaptation and the self-development of adolescents was retained.
Hypothesis two (Ho2): There is no relationship between locus of control	Spearman's rho test	Statistically, there was a significant and positive relationship between locus of control and self-development ($P\text{-value}=0.000<0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation value ($R=0.235^{**}$) implied that self-development was more

and the self-development of adolescents.		likely when they adequately control their behavior in their environment. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between locus of control and the self-development was rejected and the alternative that there is a significant relationship between locus of control and self-development of adolescents was retained.
Hypothesis three (Ho3): There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and the self-development of adolescents	Spearman's rho test	Statistically, there was a significant and positive relationship between self-efficacy and self-development (P-value=0.000<0.05). The positive sign of the correlation value (R=0.311**) implied that self-development was more likely when they portray high self-efficacy about their own self. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy the self-development of adolescents was rejected and the alternative that there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and self-development of adolescents was retrained meanwhile (34.7%) of the students do not have.
Hypothesis four (Ho4): There is no significant relationship between persistence and the self-development of adolescents	Spearman's rho test	Statistically, there was a significant and positive relationship between persistence and self-development (P-value=0.000<0.05). The positive sign of the correlation value (R=0.244**) implied that self-development was more likely when they portray high level of persistence in their environment. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between persistence and the self-development of adolescent was rejected and the alternative that there is a significant relationship between persistence and self-development of adolescents was retained.

DISCUSSIONS

Adaptation and the self-development of adolescents

Findings revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between adaptation and the self-development of adolescents in secondary school. The positive sign of the correlation implied that self-development was more likely when adolescent students adapted better in their school environment. This means that because of adaptation, students can cope in adverse circumstances. This finding is in congruence with Masten, Best and Garmezy [8] and Lewis [27] who argued that adolescents who display resilience by coping and adapting in all problems always find it easy to succeed in life. This also corresponds to Catalano, Berglund, Ryan, Lonczak, and Hawkins [28] who opined that adolescents who adapt by coping well are always less stressful thereby giving them healthy development. Grotberg [17] also argued that adolescents who display resilience by coping are more likely to overcome their initial traumatic life experiences. Thus, cultivating resilience is an important way to promote the psychological and social development of adolescents. This ties with Marcia's [66] theory that holds that adolescents who have gone through the identity crisis and come out with a well-defined self-concept, who are committed to a set of personal values, beliefs and goals have reached the state of identity achievement.

Furthermore, adolescents agreed that they are happy in all situations in life, they are not always affected by emotions and they try to do their work no matter how difficult it is. Bandura [30] equally agreed that individual with high self-esteem are always happy which makes them tend to try harder at the task and experience more positive emotions relating to the task. And Locke & Luthan's [67] theory also stipulated that setting goals provides adolescents with motivation to move beyond failure and maintain the path toward the goals which makes them to be happy throughout the life time.

Similarly, Hains & Herrman, [60] posited that there are significant links between adolescent happiness and their self-development and social problem solving abilities. Simons-Morton [68] found that adolescents who are always happy have increased rates of succeeding in life goals than those that lack such abilities. To him, adolescents may benefit from learning how to effectively adapt with peer pressure. On the contrary adolescents whose peer group engages in risk-taking behaviours tend to engage in these behaviours themselves [69].

In addition, adolescents reported that they still continued to do their daily activities despite trauma and deprivations and taking risk makes them gain more. This is in support with Todis [70] who opined that adolescents who are successful are those who have high adaptive skills, optimistic outlook, determination, and a strong future orientation. Mandleco and Peery [71] also added that adolescents with adaptive behaviours and who were involved in risk taking at 15 years of age are more resilient with a more positive self-concept and higher scores on a self-appreciation scale. This is in line with Benson [72] who postulated that resilience indicates a paradigm shift from the identification of the risk factors of an individual to the identification of strengths of an individual. According to Garmezy [73] a resilient individual is stress-resistant and less vulnerable despite experiences of significant adversity. On the same vein, Richardson, [23] argued that a resilient adolescents always return to normal functioning with the support of protective factors after encountering a severe stressor.

Locus of control and the self-development of adolescents

The findings revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between locus of control and self-development. The positive sign of the correlation implied that self-development was more likely when they adequately control their behaviour in their environment. This means that the more the adolescents exhibit locus of control behaviour, the better they become in self-development tendencies. This also implies that adolescents believed strongly that they have control over situations that affect their lives. This is in support of Haggbloom, Warnick & Warnick, [74] who argued that individuals with a strong internal locus of control believe that the responsibility for whether or not they get reinforced ultimately lies with themselves and that success or failure is due to their own efforts. This also matches with Snyder [75] who argued that hopeful people not only energetically pursue goals, it appears they may also generate more goals; and that hope reflects the capacity of an individual to conceptualize goals, develop pathways to achieve these goals, and initiate and sustain the motivation required to achieve them.

The findings also revealed that success in school is as a result of individual hard work and students always succeed in subjects where they aim high. This is in line with Shinde & Joshi [53] who agreed that individuals with an internal locus of control believe that they can control their life events because their behaviour is determined by internal factors like hard work, decision-making, problem solving skills, effort, and persuasion. In addition adolescents with an internal locus of control hold internal factors responsible for their success or failure and as a result, they become more self-reliant in achieving their goals [53]. This is also supported by Weiner [76] who argued that adolescents with higher ratings of self esteem and with higher school achievement tend to attribute success to internal, stable and controllable factors such as ability.

Conversely, individuals with an external locus of control believe their behaviour is the result of external factors like luck, fate, chance, and the people around them. Students with an external locus of control limit further improvement of their own skills, abilities, strengths, and weaknesses by relying on external factors. Similarly, those with external locus of control often view life as uncontrollable and difficult to cope with and often hold superstitious beliefs [53]. Weiner [76] equally argued that adolescents' failure in school is due to internal, unstable and controllable factors such as effort or external, uncontrollable factors such as task difficulty.

Adolescent students equally agreed that they do not feel discouraged when they make mistakes. This means that the more internal locus of control seems to be better off, they tend to be more achievement oriented and able to resist with challenges. Having an internal locus of control can also be referred to as resilient, personal control, and self-determination [77]. This compares with Bandura [78] who maintained that people can make change happen by pursuing an active life that increases the number of fortuitous encounters they are likely to experience. Thus, people's proactive efforts center on cultivating personal attributes that enable people to make the most of opportunities that arise unexpectedly from time to time. This is in congruence with the hope theory by Snyder [75] which stipulated that, hope enables adolescents to set valued goals, to see the means to achieve those goals, and to find the drive to make those goals happen. This research was also confirmed by the empirical work of Kutanis, Mesci, and Ovdur [55] who examined the effect of locus of control on students' learning outcome and found that learning outcomes of students with internal locus of control were high, and that such students were more proactive and effective during the learning process whereas those with external locus of control were more passive and reactive.

Self-efficacy and the self-development of adolescents

There was a significant and positive relationship between self-efficacy and self-development. The positive sign of the correlation implied that self-development was more likely developed they portray high students will better developed their self when they portray high self-efficacy about their own self. This implies that the more adolescents scored high self-esteem, the better their self-development. This also means that the confidence, respect or worth that adolescents have in their own selves affects their self-development efforts. This is in line with Bandura [79] who asserts that self-efficacy is an essential component of initiative. Kassin [80] also opined that individuals having high self-esteem exhibit characteristics such as expecting successfulness, being happy, making more effort, and may ignore the unnecessary things in life. This is also in line with Bandura [29] who argued that self-ability makes people to attempt things they believe they can accomplish and will not attempt things they believe they will fail. Bandura [30] also asserted that self-ability helps individuals' with high self-efficacy to try harder things which makes them gain experiences and experience more positive emotions relating to the task.

Furthermore, students equally revealed that they attempt even things they cannot accomplish and have high expectations about themselves. This is in agreement with Yelsma & Yelsma [40] who argued that, the individuals having high self-esteem prefer much more difficult activities, seem to be quite sure of their efforts resulting in success, are less sensitive against emotional turbulences, are less affected by depression, are more open to accept critical analyses from efficient people, state less negative effects and do not experience negative effect when they notice that others are superior to them. This is also in congruence with Pajare [81] who opined that self-efficacy beliefs influence individual thought

and action and emotional reactions as people with high self-efficacy always believe that nothing is tougher than them.

In the study, adolescents believed in their self-abilities, take initiative to overcome difficult situations, and have high expectations about their future. This was in line with Coleman & Hendry [82] who stated that those possessing high self-esteem show happiness toward situations, are healthy, productive and successful, make much longer effort to overcome the difficulties, sleep better at nights, have less risk in developing illness, show less tendency against accepting others and the pressures of their peers; those having low self-esteem, on the other hand, are individuals who are worried, pessimistic, having negative thoughts about future and having tendency of unsuccessfulness. And Bandura [83] added that adolescents with a strong sense of efficacy and initiative enhance human accomplishment and personal well-being in many ways, since people with high assurance in their capabilities approach difficult tasks as challenges to be mastered rather than as threats to be avoided. Such an efficacious outlook fosters intrinsic interest and deep engrossment in activities [84]. He attributed failure to insufficient effort or deficient knowledge and skills which are acquirable. Such an efficacious outlook produces personal accomplishments, reduces stress and lowers vulnerability to depression [84].

Similarly, Greene & Way [85] posited that self-esteem has been shown to be an indicator of overall wellbeing and is linked to positive psychological and behavioural outcomes for youth. Leory [86] equally revealed that self-esteem states the personal and total feelings of self-value, self-confidence or self-acceptance. Also, Salami [87] opined that in the concept of self, people believe that they are talented, successful, worthy and important. Self-esteem focuses on the person's need to evaluate himself or positively evaluate himself. Positive self-esteem is described as accepting, appreciating and trusting oneself entirely as an individual [88]. This is in line with Rosenberg [89] who maintained that high self-esteem persons have respect and feeling of worthiness and yet acknowledge their faults and shortcomings. This matches with Snyder [75] who maintained that people with more hope tend to be successful in their goal pursuits and, as a result, tend to experience more positive emotions, while people with less hope tend to have more difficulty in overcoming the barriers to goal attainment.

Persistence and the self-development of the adolescents

There was a significant and positive relationship between persistence and self-development. The positive sign of the correlation implied that self-development was more likely when they portray high level of persistence in their environment. This also means that the ability of adolescents to stand firm or obstinate continuance in a course of action influences their self-development. From the findings, it was revealed that students enjoy performing challenging task. This is in line with Wong [90] who indicates that adolescents performing challenging work use it as an opportunity for them to learn new skills and they believe they have a bright future. Adolescents are more likely to persist in their goal pursuit, when many response options are available; they persist as long as they are free to explore alternative pathways to success [90]. Not often giving up in the face of challenges as the study showed tie with Anderson, Costa and Kallick [91] who pointed out that adolescent student persistence is seen as “sticking to it and not giving up.” However, as adolescents develop, it is hoped that their ideas would deepen to define persistence as keeping goals in mind, identifying obstacles toward achieving the goals, and finding effective ways around them [91]. Hoppe [44] represents persistence as a person's expectations, goals, claims or his future achievement in a given task. He further stresses that the “experiences of performance” as a success of failure does not depend upon its objective goodness alone but also on the persistence reached.

In contrast, Schwarzer [90] argued that people who doubt their capabilities shy away from difficult tasks which they view as personal threats. They have low aspirations and weak commitment to the goals they choose to pursue. According to him, when adolescents are faced with difficult tasks, they dwell on their personal deficiencies, on the obstacles they will encounter, and all kinds of adverse outcomes rather than concentrate on how to perform successfully. They slacken their efforts and give up quickly in the face of difficulties. That is there are slow to recover their sense of efficacy following failure or setbacks.

Adolescents equally agreed that they have what it takes to socialize with their friends. Morrow & Ackermann [45] posited that positive interactions with other members of the adolescent or college community promote adjustment to the demands of college. Tinto [46] also added that the utility of college or adolescent subcultures and student-teacher interaction have a positive impact on their development. Therefore, greater integration with the school community is essential to academic success. In fact, living on campus dramatically increases students persisting to continue and aspiring to succeed [93]. Turner [94] noted that integrating male adolescents into the social framework of college is a key step in encouraging persistence. For examples, intramural sports teams, fraternities, and learning communities encourage a sense of belonging [94]. This is needed because societal values surrounding masculinity emphasize “strength and power” [95] and positive influence. This was contrary to Sanders [96] who believed that socialization with friends was full of negative consequences which make adolescents not to persist but instead drop out from school.

In addition, adolescents said that, doing the same thing over and over motivate them to finish their task. Adolescents also reported that they often put in effort until they finish a task. In the same way, Snyder [97] maintained that cognitive set involve the self-perception that one can produce routes to desired goals (the pathways component), with the motivation to use them to attain desired goals. This ties with Bandura [29] who argued that efficacious people set challenging goals and maintain strong commitment to them and in the face of impending failure they increase and sustain their efforts to be successful. This also ties with Erikson [98] who reported that purpose helps young people to successfully navigate and resolve their identity crisis. Moreover, a strong sense of purpose underscores pro-social action and civic engagement. This matches with Bandura [99] socio-cognitive theory who argued that confident students anticipate successful outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this study was to investigate into resilience effects on the self-development of adolescents in Kumba II Sub Division of the South West Region of Cameroon. Resilient indicators were adaptation, locus of control, self-esteem and persistence which were tested against self-development. The findings indicated that adolescents possessed adaptability skills which were very useful for self-development. They remained significantly engaged in their daily activities despite trauma and deprivation they suffer as adversities. Moreover adolescents have problems solving abilities which make them happy in life. We also found positive relationships between adaptation and self-development and argue that adolescent adaptation helps them lessen depression, anxiety, stress and psychological problems which have a significant impact on their self-development and achievement.

The study has also revealed that the more adolescents exhibit locus of control behaviour, the better they become in self-development initiatives. This implies that adolescents believed strongly that they have control over the situations that affect their lives. Their success in school is as a result of individual hard work, and students always succeed in subjects where they aim high. Adolescents were found to have control over their situations and do not feel discouraged when they make mistakes. With these, scores on locus of control behaviour which also affects self-development were also high. Bandura [79] asserts that self-control leads to resilience as individuals act on specific plans focusing on the transformation of the external environment to match self-set aspirations. Furthermore, adolescents with external locus of control determine their behaviours according to other people's wills, needs, perceptions and interpretations rather than their own. On the other hand, people who have internal locus determine their behaviour according to their own wills, needs, perception and interpretations.

Equally, adolescents possessed in them self-efficacy that determined their self-development potentials. That is adolescents often belief on their-ability, attempt even things they cannot accomplish and have high expectation about their self. Adolescents' students agreed they can always take initiative to overcome difficulties. Therefore, accepting that they could overcome these adversities despite the daunting times, it could therefore concluded that adolescent students possessed in them resilience that determines the self-development of adolescents in schools. Emler [100] maintained that self-esteem is how people feel about themselves and their self-worth which is often influenced by achievement alone. Thus, adolescents were found to be positive about themselves and this optimistic feeling gave ground to adolescent self-development. Thus, adolescent possessed in them self-efficacy. Equally, adolescents possessed in them self-esteem that determined their self-development potentials.

Finally, adolescents were found to be persistence when they encounter challenges as they enjoyed doing challenging task, do not give up when they are face with challenges and have what it takes to socialized with friends. It could therefore concluded that adolescent students possessed in them resilience that determines their self-development in schools. Benard [101] contented that, "we are all born with an innate capacity for resilience and persistence, by which we are able to develop social competence, problem-solving skills, a critical consciousness, autonomy, and a sense of purpose". Whether and how we do so, depends predominantly, on one hand, on the protective factors that are available to us and to which we've been exposed and on the other hand, the risk factors to which we have been exposed to because there will be no need for resilience without adversities.

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